

PRESCHOOL EDUCATION - A NEW RECOMMENDATION IN THE SOCIO-EMOTIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS AS THE FOUNDATION OF A SYSTEM OF CONTINUING EDUCATION.

Sevara Jamolova

Educator of Preschool institution No. 9 in Karshi district

Annotation: This article analyzes the educational significance of the use of forms, methods and tools of new methods in the socio-emotional development of students.

Keywords: training, interactive method, tool, didactic purpose, socio-emotional development, education, ethics.

Scientific observations and research have shown that seventy percent of all the information a person receives during his or her lifetime can be obtained by the age of five. Indeed, in this period, the human child understands the world, learns his native language, awakens love for parents, family, neighborhood, homeland, prepares the ground for lifelong knowledge. In this case, first of all, if the family plays a key role, the contribution of the preschool education institution is also important in this regard. Therefore, in our country, preschool education has become an integral part of the system of continuing education, in other words, its prelude. In this regard, the recently published resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of preschool education in 2017-2021" will undoubtedly serve to raise the system to a new level, modernize the sector at today's level. Of course, the focus on this issue did not appear yesterday or today.

In retrospect, over the past 25 years of independence, under the leadership of the First President Islam Karimov, important steps have been taken to radically reform education in our country, forming a system of continuing education that does not exist in any other country. In other words, the creation of conditions for

continuous education and vocational training of the younger generation from preschool to higher education has become a priority of state policy.

In this regard, the development of the system of preschool education, the involvement of children in preschool education, preparation for school was considered one of the priorities of state policy in the field of education. First of all, favorable organizational and legal conditions have been created in our country for the upbringing of a harmoniously developed generation.

President Shavkat Mirziyoyev has consistently pursued reforms in this area, focusing on the development of the network of preschool education institutions in accordance with modern requirements and standards, their reconstruction and modernization are included.

In particular, the program for further improvement of the preschool education system for 2017-2021, approved by the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, is significant in that it sets a wide range of strategic goals and important tasks. In particular, we are pleased that the document takes into account today's vital needs and requirements, issues that need to be addressed in the field, as well as untapped opportunities.

Especially, over the next five years, strengthening the material and technical base of 2,200 preschool institutions, including the construction of new preschools institutions in rural areas, providing them with modern inventory, equipment, teaching aids, multimedia resources and a total of The fact that 2.2 trillion soums are planned to be allocated shows how wide the scope of this decision is.

Indeed, today there is a need to dramatically increase the number of preschools in rural areas. For young mothers living in some rural settings, the issue of kindergarten has become a vital necessity. Of course, this need is not in vain. Preschool education serves, firstly, to raise the general literacy of preschool children, to instill in children a sense of patriotism, pride in it, to teach the Constitution, to broaden their horizons, and secondly, to realize the constitutional right of mothers to work. In addition, there is a need to increase the number of kindergartens for children from young families in the new housing estates being built in the regions

on the basis of standard projects. According to the resolution, based on foreign experience and climatic conditions of the country, it is planned to build 50 modern preschools for 70 and 120 places on the basis of standard designs and expand 1167 of them by reconstruction and 983 by overhauling them. This will increase the coverage of children in preschool education by 1.5 times. At the same time, the decision provides for a 30 percent reduction in parental fees in preschools in rural areas, which will provide relief for low-income and large families.

Of course, it is difficult to imagine the effect of reforms in this area without personnel who can fully meet the requirements of the industry. Therefore, the issue of creating a mechanism for continuous improvement of the skills of teachers in the system through advanced methods, the widespread application of information and communication technologies in the educational process, the improvement of continuous methodological services is also relevant.

Taking these factors into account, the resolution sets the task to improve the training and professional development curricula and programs for preschool education, taking into account modern pedagogical technologies and methods. Because we have set ourselves the goal of creating the necessary conditions for the full intellectual, moral, aesthetic and physical development of our children, there is no doubt that we need to improve the existing experience in improving the skills of teachers at the level of modern requirements. At the same time, the provision of preschools with specialists such as psychologists, speech pathologists is also a requirement of today.

At the same time, the role of short-term training groups is important in preparing children for school who are not covered by preschool education. For this reason, in the future it is planned to create 6,100 short-term groups as an alternative form of preparing children for school. In addition, it is advisable to increase the pedagogical and psychological knowledge of parents in the preparation of children not involved in preschool education. The resolution of the head of state pays special attention to the organization of preparation of children aged 3-6 for school education by providing their parents with methodological manuals, which will increase the

level of preparation of children for the next stage of education. In this regard, it is necessary to continue the tradition of intellectual, physical, moral education of preschool children, acquaintance with universal values, the organization of various clubs, spiritual and ecological rooms, small museums, libraries to prepare children for school. Because the interest in books, art, science, in general, to take a certain profession in the future is formed in children at the same time. The following games will help to develop the social and emotional development of students.

I WILL BE HAPPY

Now, I will tell you an example of when I was happy, and you will tell me your example one after another. For example, I am very happy when the first snow falls. So, dear, when will you be happy? (Aziz, I'm happy when they bring sweets, Aziza says I'm happy when they bring me a new doll.) The game ends with each child in the group giving an example. The educator rewards the child with the book who said the best examples.

THE CAT THAT MADE HIS MOTHER HAPPY

The tutor reads the following story. There used to be a cat. He has everything. Notebooks, toys, cars, everything is there. But he was bored with playing with toys and drawing. When he was so bored, he noticed the unwashed dishes in the kitchen. She was tired from work, she thought she would be happy to wash the dishes, and she washed the dishes. The kitten's mother came home from work happy and kissed the kitten, saying that she should share the joy with others. Oh, guys, who knows how to please their mother. For example, my daughter fixes her shoes at home every day. What about you, Nafisa? Nafisa says that she adjusts her position every day and Sardor helps her brother to collect toys.

THE PRINCESS THAT DOESN'T LAUGH

The educator asks the pupils where a princess knows how to make her happy if she never knows how to laugh. The children make suggestions to make the princess happy. For example, Akmal tells the prince a cheerful poem, and Salima tells him to give his doll to the princess to play with. Komila invites Malika to her house. In this way, each child in the group makes a proposal and makes the princess happy.

In short, preschool education is the primary part of continuing education. It stimulates the child's desire to learn, prepares him for systematic learning, ensuring that he develops into a healthy and developed person. Therefore, the further strengthening of this system, the creation of all-round favorable conditions in preschool education institutions, the wide involvement of preschool children in them play an important role in the formation of our children as harmonious and mature individuals.